

GENOME STRUCTURE OF HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS: E6 AND E7. KEY DATA ON HPV AND HPV-RELATED CANCERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *Human papillomavirus (HPV) is a common virus, that causes cancerous diseases in both men and women. The route of transmission is mainly through sexual contact, but also through close contact of infected parts of the skin and mucous membranes of the organs with the virus. Infection with HPV results in cervical cancer in women: high mortality rates from cervical cancer are observed due to late diagnosis and poor prognosis. In 93% of cases, cause of cervical cancer is papillomaviruses, of which 70% are HPV-16 and 18 types. Initial establishment and progression of cancer are completely depend on two major oncogenes E6 and E7. In the present article, information on structural, functional, and clinical dimensions of E6 and E7 activity has been reviewed. The main part of the article presents the incidence of HPV in Uzbekistan, including the crude incidence rates of HPV-related cancers and burden of cervical cancer in women.*

Key words: *human papillomavirus, oncoproteins E6 and E7, cervical cancer, crude incidence rates of HPV-related cancers, burden of cervical cancer.*

INTRODUCTION

Human papillomaviruses (HPV) are a group of DNA-viruses belonging to the family Papillomaviridae, which includes more than 200 types (strains). The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that the prevalence of HPV infection between nine and thirteen percent or about 630 million people [1]. Overall, 5.2% of all cancers worldwide can be attributed to HPV infection [2].

Papillomaviruses are divided into two types according to the severity of the disease they cause: low-risk (non-oncogenic) and high-risk (oncogenic). low-risk types (non-oncogenic) associated with anogenital warts (condyloma acuminata), oral and conjunctival papillomas, recurrent respiratory papillomatosis (in infants and young children), and mild dysplasia [3]. High-risk types (oncogenic) are associated with high-grade dysplasia and various cancers [3]. Among the high-risk types, HPV

16 is undoubtedly the most frequently detected genotype in 60.5% of cervical cancer cases, followed by HPV18 (Serrano et al., 2017).

GENOME STRUCTURE OF HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS.

The HPV genome structure and the oncogenes have been discussed in this section with reference to high-risk HPV16 type (*figure-1*). The HPV-16 genome is a 7.9 kb long nucleotide belt, segmented into three sections: the *early* gene-coding region (E), the *late* gene-coding region (L), and the *long control region* (LCR), also called as *non-coding region* (NCR) or *upstream regulatory region* (URR) [4]. The 5' end begins with the *early gene coding region*, which has six open reading frames, named as E1, E2, E4, E5, E6, and E7. E1 and E2 are known to regulate the replication of the viral genome and transcription of early proteins, while E5–E7 are the ones inducing oncogenesis. E5 is known to help in keratinocyte differentiation and immune evasion during the later stages, while E6 and E7 take in charge of several cellular checkpoints to establish the cancer hallmarks (*Table-1*). The late gene coding section has two parts: L1 and L2. L1 codes for a major viral capsid protein, while L2 codes for a minor viral capsid structure (*Table-1*). Although the 850 bp stretch of LCR does not contain any protein coding sequence, it contains the origin of replication and numerous transcription factor binding sites for RNA polymerase II facilitated transcription.

Figure-1. HPV-16 genome
(*Table-1*)

GENE		FUNCTION
Late genes	L1	-Major capsid protein.
	L2	-Minor capsid protein.

Early genes	E1	-Transcription factor, DNA-helicase activity; -Mediates episomal DNA replication.
	E2	-Initiation of viral DNA replication; - Transcription factor, regulates transcription of E6 and E7.
	E4	-Facilitates virion release.
	E5	-Stimulates cell proliferation and prevents differentiation: enhances growth factor signaling pathways.
	E6	-Deregulates cell cycle control through p53 degradation.
	E7	-pRb mediated deregulation of cell cycle.

HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS: E6 AND E7 ONCOPROTEINS.

HPVs encode two oncoproteins, E6 and E7, which are directly responsible for the development of HPV-induced carcinogenesis. (*Figure-2*). Both E6 and E7 are transcribed polycistronically from a single promoter located at the 3' end of the upstream regulatory region (URR). E6/E7 transcription is under the regulation of several transcription factors such as AP1 and SP1, which functions by binding to the URR region. E7 was the first oncogene to be discovered, among all the HPV oncogenes. It is a relatively small phosphoprotein of about 100 amino acids, with three conserved regions 1/2/3 (CR1/2/3) (Phelps et al., 1988).

E7 oncoprotein deregulates the cell cycle by means of retinoblastoma protein pRb, which is 110 kDa in size of the host cell. It is a tumor suppressor protein that prevents excessive cell growth. If not mutated, it is present in our cells and blocks the growth of dysfunctional cells between the G1 and S phase of the cell cycle before they can undergo DNA replication. pRb also regulates the function of cyclin and cyclin dependent kinase (CDK) complexes which are needed for the cell to proceed with cell growth. E2F is a transcription factor that forms a complex with pRb to inhibit cell growth. When E2F is not bound to pRb it encourages cells to proliferate, it's main function is to express genes required for DNA replication to take place. [9]. As a result, the cell cycle is deregulated: between G1 and the S-

phase, the growth of dysfunctional cells does not stop and unrestricted entry into S-phase in the cell (*Figure-2*).

On the other hand, E6 is relatively larger protein with 150–160 amino acids coding an 18 kDa protein (Zanier et al., 2012). It is arranged into two zinc finger binding domains by four Cys-X-X-Cys motifs, which have been found to be responsible for the oncogenicity of the protein (Nomine et al., 2006). E6 oncoprotein blocks apoptosis by p53 protein of host cell and disrupts proliferation of the cell [6]. E6-mediated inhibition of p53 allows several cellular changes to turn a cell oncogenic, one of them being induction of uncontrolled cell proliferation by evading the cellular checkpoints. The 53 kD molecular weight protein, p53, is the most wellcharacterized tumor suppressor protein till date and is often called as the “guardian of the genome” since it decides the fate of a cell during stressed conditions. E6 has been found to degrade p53 through ubiquitination with the help of E6AP (E6-associated protein also known as UBE3A. This molecule binds to p53 transcription factor in the cell, which controls programmed cell death and participates in the regulation of the cell cycle, and degrades the p53 molecule. (*Figure-2*). As a result, p53 is unable to block BCl-2, Bax, and Bak modulators that disrupt apoptosis, and programmed cell death is disrupted and cell numbers increase dramatically. [7]. Deregulation of the cell cycle and proliferative processes, blockage of apoptosis lead to tissue tumors.

KEY DATA ON HPV AND HPV-RELATED CANCERS IN UZBEKISTAN.

Uzbekistan has a population of 11.9 millions women ages 15 years and older who are at risk of developing cervical cancer. Current estimates indicate that every year 1887 women are diagnosed with cervical cancer and 1103 die from the disease. Cervical cancer ranks as the 2nd most frequent cancer among women in Uzbekistan and the 2nd most frequent cancer among women between 15 and 44 years of age. Data is not yet available on the HPV burden in the general population of Uzbekistan (*Table-2*) [8]. High-risk HPV infections have been linked to cervical cancer, anogenital cancer, oropharyngeal cancer, and laryngeal cancer (*Table-3*). Cervical cancer has the highest rate among women in Uzbekistan with a coefficient of 11.3. Among men, oral cancer has a coefficient of 3.73 [8].

Figure-2 ¹. E6 mediated p53 manipulation and E7 mediated inhibition of pRb protein.. Uncontrolled cell proliferation. Blockade of apoptosis.

Table-2. Burden of cervical cancer

	Incidence	Mortality
Annual number of new cases/deaths	1887	1103
Crude rate	11.3	6.58
Age-standardized rate	11.0	6.68
Cumulative risk 0—74 years (%)	1.17	0.76
Ranking of cervical cancer (all years)	2nd	3rd
Ranking of cervical cancer (15—44 years)	2nd	2nd

Table-3. Crude incidence rates of HPV-related cancers

Cancerous disease	Male	Female
Cervical cancer	-	11.3
Anal cancer	1.02	0.80
Vulva cancer	-	0.45
Vaginal cancer	-	0.22

¹ The scheme belongs to the author

Penile cancer	0.04	-
Oropharyngeal cancer	1.01	0.58
Oral cavity cancer	3.73	1.80
Laryngeal cancer	0.90	0.28

CONCLUSION

Diseases caused by human papillomavirus and viral infections are one of the most pressing issues for healthcare professionals. This is because although a number of vaccines have been developed and put into practice to prevent the spread of the virus, no cure has been found.

Cervical cancer ranks as the 2nd most frequent cancer among women in Uzbekistan and the 2nd most frequent cancer among women between 15 and 44 years of age. Data is not yet available on the HPV burden in the general population of Uzbekistan. However, in Asia, about 3.4% of women in the general population are estimated to harbour cervical HPV-16/18 infection at a given time, and 68.9% of invasive cervical cancers are attributed to HPVs 16 or 18 [8].

HPVs encode two oncoproteins, E6 and E7, which are directly responsible for the development of HPV-induced carcinogenesis. E6 mediated p53 manipulation and E7 mediated inhibition of pRb protein leading to sustained cell proliferation and resistance to apoptotic barrier.

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